

Marketing activities management system

The subject of the research is the theoretical principles of marketing management of agricultural enterprises in Ukraine.

The purpose of the study is to determine the nature and role of marketing management in the enterprise, to determine the stages of the marketing management system to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Research methods. The system approach, dialectical method of scientific knowledge, analysis and synthesis, method of comparison and generalization of data are used in the work.

Results of work. The article analyzes the modern approaches to defining the essence of management, which allowed to clarify the concept of «enterprise management system». The study of the elements of the system, which include the purpose and objectives, subsystems, functions, subject, object, principles and support. The purpose of the marketing management system is to bring the existing state of the system to the desired state.

Field of application. Marketing.

Conclusions. The content of functions and principles of the enterprise management system is revealed. The definition of «marketing management system» as a set of elements whose relationship is provided by the purposeful action of the subject on the object, which is organized to provide the subsystem of marketing management subsystem desired state, which differs from existing disclosure of the relationship of individual elements marketing systems, taking into account the purpose, as well as complexity.

Key words: marketing, marketing activity, principles of marketing, management of marketing activity of the enterprise, approaches to management of marketing activity, purposes of marketing activity.

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Система управління маркетинговою діяльністю підприємств

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні засади управління маркетинговою діяльністю аграрних підприємств в Україні.

Метою дослідження є визначення сутності та ролі управління маркетингом на підприємстві, визначення етапів системи маркетингового менеджменту для підвищення ефективності та конкурентоспроможності підприємства.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані системний підхід, діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, аналіз та синтез, метод порівняння та узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті проведено аналіз сучасних підходів до визначення сутності управління, що дало змогу конкретніше дати уточнення поняттю «система управління підприємством». Проведено дослідження елементів системи, до яких відносять мету та завдання, підсистеми, функції, суб'єкт, об'єкт, принципи та забезпечення. Мета системи управління маркетинговою діяльністю полягає в приведенні існуючого стану системи в бажаний стан.

Галузь застосування. Маркетинг.

Висновки. Розкрито зміст функцій і принципів системи управління підприємством. Уточнено визначення поняття «система управління маркетинговою діяльністю» як сукупність елементів взаємозв'язок яких забезпечений цілеспрямованою дією суб'єкта на об'єкт, яка організована з метою надання підсистемі управління маркетинговою діяльністю бажаного стану, що відрізняється від існуючих розкриттям змісту взаємозв'язку окремих елементів системи маркетингу, врахуванням мети, а також комплексністю.

Ключові слова: маркетинг, маркетингова діяльність, принципи маркетингу, управління маркетинговою діяльністю підприємства, підходи до управління маркетинговою діяльністю, цілі маркетингової діяльності.

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Система управления маркетинговой деятельностью предприятий

Предметом исследования являются теоретические основы управления маркетинговой деятельностью аграрных предприятий в Украине.

Целью исследования является определение сущности и роли управления маркетингом на предприятии, определение этапов системы маркетингового менеджмента для повышения эффективности и конкурентоспособности предприятия. способы исследования.

Способы исследования. В работе использован системный подход, диалектический метод научного познания, анализ и синтез, метод сравнения и обобщения данных.

Результаты работы. В статье проведен анализ современных подходов к определению сущности управления, что позволило конкретнее дать уточнение понятию «система управления предприятием». Проведены исследования элементов системы, к которым относятся цель и задачи, подсистемы, функции, субъект, объект, принципы и обеспечение. Цель системы управления маркетинговой деятельностью состоит в приведении существующего состояния системы в желаемое состояние.

Область применения. Маркетинг.

Выводы. Раскрыто содержание функций и принципов системы управления предприятием. Уточнено определение понятия «система управления маркетинговой деятельностью» как совокупность элементов взаимосвязь которых обеспечена целенаправленным действием субъекта на объект, организованная с целью предоставления подсистеме управления маркетинговой деятельностью желаемого состояния, отличающегося от существующих раскрытием содержания взаимосвязи отдельных элементов системы маркетинга, учетом целей, а также комплексностью.

Ключевые слова: маркетинг, маркетинговая деятельность, принципы маркетинга, управление маркетинговой деятельностью предприятия, подходы к управлению маркетинговой деятельностью, цели маркетинговой деятельности.

Formulation of the problem. One of the most effective tools to influence the results of the enterprise is the management of marketing activities. Given the changing business climate, characterized by increasing competition, imperfect system of government regulation, it is necessary to improve the company as a whole and, in particular, its marketing component, which will enable them to increase their competitive advantage in domestic and foreign markets. Exacerbation of the competitive environment necessitates the search for new approaches to ensuring high competitiveness of the enterprise.

The reason for the lack of profitability of enterprises is an inefficient marketing management system. A significant proportion of enterprises today need timely adaptation to changes in the environment in which they operate, in solving strategic tasks and in maintaining a competitive position in the market. This problem is increasingly faced by domestic en-

terprises, as most of them do not use or use at a relatively low level of the marketing component as one of the main elements of effective economic activity. Thus, the study of improving the management of marketing activities of enterprises and the development on this basis of the necessary guidelines is quite relevant in today's market conditions.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Research of problems of management of marketing activity of the enterprise has been reflected in works of such scientists: A.V. Voychak, M.V. Volkova, T.D. Girchenko, I.M. Komarnytsky, I.G. Klimova, I.V. Mosiychuk, A.V. Tkachenko, I.O. Shcheblikina and others. The question of assessing the effectiveness of marketing activities is reflected in the works of a number of domestic economists, among which should be noted the work of L.V. Balabanova, V.A. Shapovalova, N.V. Butenka, N.K. Moiseeva, A.F. Pavlenko, V.A. Parkhi-

menko, T.E. Derevyanchenko, A. Reznichenko and others. However, according to research results, in the domestic scientific literature there is no comprehensive study of the management of marketing activities in a competitive environment.

The purpose of the article is to determine the nature and role of marketing management in the enterprise, to determine the stages of the marketing management system to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The issue of ensuring the effectiveness of the management system of marketing activities of the enterprise (firm, organization) can be confidently identified as the main task of economics in general. This situation is based on many factors, among which are:

- enterprise (firm, organization) is one of the links of the economic system and the main market player in the state and it is from its efficiency, which is carried out through an effective management system, achieves sustainability of the economy as a whole;
- enterprises (firms, organizations) operate in conditions of fierce competition in a market that is oversaturated with enterprises of various forms of ownership, and therefore each of them is interested in creating a competitive and efficient management system;
- Almost all employees are members of a management system, depending on their own employment or participation in business. This determines the interest of almost market participants in the

quality and efficiency of the management system of marketing activities of the enterprise.

The study of theoretical and practical aspects of management is devoted to the work of many scientists: some scientists study the theoretical and organizational principles of management, others – practical aspects, some scientists study foreign experience and try to adapt it to national conditions. taking into account the characteristics of a particular enterprise. However, in our opinion, the study of the theoretical basis of the outlined issue needs the most attention, because the theoretical research is the basis of effective practical decisions and results. Therefore, we focus on existing definitions of management (Table 1).

As can be seen from table. 1, approaches to the definition of «management» are sufficiently different from each other, but more generally such approaches can be outlined as follows:

- management as a process of distribution and movement of all resources;
- management as a purposeful action;
- management as an element, function of organizational systems;
- management as a process of planning, organization, motivation and control;
- control as a process of transferring the managed system to a predetermined state.

The approach of treating management as a process of resource allocation and movement is somewhat legitimate, but it is more appropriate

Table 1. Modern approaches to the definition of «management»

Author, source	Definition
Bolshakov A.S.	Management is the process of allocating and moving resources within an organization with a predetermined goal, a pre-designed plan, and continuous monitoring of performance.
Borisov A.B.	Management is a deliberate purposeful action by the state, economic actors on people and economic objects, carried out in order to direct their actions in the right direction and get the desired results.
Mocherny S.V.	Management is the process of planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling the formulation and achievement of an organization's goals.
Vechkanov G.S.	Management – an element, a function of organizational systems, which ensures the preservation of the structure, support for the mode of operation, program implementation, objectives. Management consists of two components: the ability to organize, including the ability to delegate authority, and intuition.
Economic encyclopedic vocabulary	Management – conscious, purposeful action of entities on individuals, labor collectives and wider communities, as well as on economic objects in order to achieve these goals and ensure the stability and dynamism of the managed object. Management can also be considered as a set of processes of planning, organization of coordination, motivation, control and implementation of economic property relations in order to achieve the goals set by the subjects.

Source: generated by the author according to [1–4].

to define resource allocation as the process that accompanies management rather than as a substantive feature of management itself.

Management as a purposeful action to some extent limits the essence of management due to the fact that purposeful action only reveals the content of the subject's influence on the object [1, p. 149].

An approach that considers management as an element or function of organizational systems reveals the content of the organizational system as an orderly construction. [2, p. 451]. At the same time, the essence of management in this approach remains undisclosed.

Management as a process of planning, organization, motivation and control reduces the essence of management to a list of well-known functions of management, which also generally narrows the essence of the concept of management [3].

The most appropriate, in our opinion, is the approach according to which management is the process of translating a controlled system into a predetermined state [4, p. 153].

This approach can be fully considered appropriate and comprehensive, and therefore can serve as a basis for clarifying the concept of «enterprise management system».

Therefore, there is an objective need to consider the principles of such a system.

The system is often interpreted as a set of certain elements and connections between them, which are characterized by signs of integrity and the presence of a common goal. The elements of the system usually include the purpose and objectives, subsystems, functions, subject, object, principles and support.

Therefore, first of all, it is advisable to determine the purpose and objectives of the marketing management system.

The purpose of the marketing management system can be most fully disclosed in the light of the above considerations as follows: the purpose of the marketing management system is to bring the existing state of the system to the desired state.

In this case, the main tasks of the management system of marketing activities can be attributed [2, p. 454]:

- organization of sales of goods and services taking into account consumer demand under the influence of both internal and external environment of the enterprise;

- transition to the use of highly qualified employees, skills that can think quickly and critically;

- incentives for employees through appropriate working conditions and pay systems;

- identification of the necessary resources and sources of marketing activities; – development of enterprise development strategy (firm, organization) and implementation of its marketing activities;

- definition of the purposes of development of the organization by marketing activity;

- development of a system of measures to achieve this goal;

- control over the effectiveness of marketing activities of the enterprise (firm, organization).

This list of tasks facing the management system of marketing activities can be considered fully exhaustive.

With regard to the subsystems of the enterprise management system, in this context it is worth noting that such subsystems are formed personally by each individual enterprise, but traditionally such subsystems include [5]:

- financial management subsystem;
- production management subsystem;
- subsystem of marketing management;
- subsystem of internal services management;
- personnel management subsystem.

If we consider the functions of the management system of marketing activities, it is appropriate to assume that the management system performs the same functions as management in general.

In turn, the main functions of management in the well-known sense of planning, organization, motivation, control.

Characteristics of the functions of the enterprise management system are given in table. 2.

Regarding the subject and object of the marketing management system, it is worth noting that this is too individual a matter, which is determined by each individual enterprise in accordance with the management structure, organizational structure of the enterprise and the characteristics of the activity.

Management of marketing activities at the enterprise is carried out in three directions: the formation of the marketing mix, management of the marketing department, internal marketing.

Thus, the model of management of marketing activities of the enterprise is a set of certain subjects, objects, tools and methods of management, which in the process of interaction are aimed at effective management of marketing activities of the enterprise.

Table 2. Characteristics of the functions of the enterprise management system

Function	Characteristics of the function
Planning	The planning function determines the production objectives, norms and standards of consumption of resources per unit of output, estimates of production costs in terms of production units of the enterprise, the financial results of economic activity. The strategy laid down in specific plans, programs developed taking into account possible changes in economic activity – the basis of successful management, and hence the survival of the enterprise.
Organization	Organization is a process that is aimed at the most optimal combination of resources – material, energy, labor, financial, information in the production process. The effect of the organization is manifested in the successful combination of all types of resources. Therefore, much of the working time of the management staff is used to organize the production process.
Motivation	Motivation, as an element of management, is aimed at making decisions and supporting them with orders, instructions, guidelines on the use of living labor and material resources, involves subordination and subordination between team members. To do this, employees are endowed with administrative and executive functions.
Control	In the general sense, control acts as a tool that provides all parts of the management apparatus with information about the state of the object of management. Control activities are to develop standards for the functioning of the system and coordination with planned tasks, creating an information system and more.

Source: formed by the author according to [6, p. 44]

It should be noted that the growing role of marketing in the activities of economic entities has gradually been reflected in the construction of organizational and managerial structures and their functions. As an economic function, marketing has gone through four stages of development, such as the distribution functions, organizational concentration (concentration on sales functions), the allocation of independent marketing services and the transformation of marketing into a general function of enterprise management. Under such conditions, the importance of internal marketing increases, which is a tool to increase employee motivation, and therefore can be considered as part of marketing management. The main functional areas that the company can use in the field of internal marketing are the organization of trainings, leadership and support, internal communications and dialogue, external communications, planning, promotion, use of technology, internal research.

In general, the subject can be described as a control subsystem, and the object – the controlled subsystems of the enterprise management system.

In this case, the influence of the subject on the object is carried out through the purposeful action, which was discussed above.

The principle is the basic, initial position of the theory, the rule of activity of the organization in any sphere, or the rule of behavior of the person.

The initial point in building an enterprise management system is the formulation of principles of marketing management. The following basic prin-

ciples of enterprise management system can be identified [6–9]:

1. The principle of reproduction of the life support system. The functioning of the enterprise as a management system should ensure the preservation of the ecosystem, resource-saving reproduction of all components of the system.

2. The principle of social orientation of the enterprise. The ultimate goal of the enterprise should be the production of goods and services necessary for society.

3. The principle of legal regulation of management. Economic and legal regulation of enterprise management processes in compliance with regulations governing the legality of management.

4. The principle of scientific validity of the management system involves taking into account economic laws and laws of thought in the formation of the system, as well as the use of scientific approaches that help increase the stability of the management system.

5. System approach to management. This approach involves the consideration of the enterprise as a system, a set of interdependent elements (subsystems), the relationship with the external environment. The systems approach allows to take into account all the necessary relationships and interactions in the management system, and when setting goals – to comprehensively weigh all the factors and direct management mechanisms to achieve goals.

6. The principle of orientation of the enterprise on an innovative way of development.

To increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, its economic development must focus on investing in innovation (mainly in new technologies and management).

7. The principle of maintaining and developing competitive advantage. Identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise allows you to form a strategy based on their forecasting, to gain a competitive advantage in the production of goods (services).

8. The principle of unity of theory and practice of management. Any management decision must comply with the logic, principles and methods of management, solving one of the practical tasks.

9. The principle of comparability of options for management decisions in their choice. Options for management decisions are presented in comparable form by the following factors: time, quality, level of development, method of obtaining information, risk factors and uncertainty.

The list of principles is not clearly declared, so the list, number and content of the principles of the enterprise management system may vary depending on the overall mission and objectives of each individual enterprise.

Given the above justification of the essence of management, taking into account the generalized management system of marketing activities, we can propose a refined definition of «marketing management system» as follows: marketing management system is a set of elements whose relationship is provided which is organized in order to provide the subsystem of marketing management of the desired state.

The proposed definition differs from the existing ones by disclosing the content of the relationship between the individual elements of the marketing system, taking into account the purpose, as well as complexity.

At the present stage of development of market relations, no company can function properly without the use of marketing to determine its market position, analyze their capabilities, study the market environment, determine development strategies and more. Therefore, marketing activities are a recognized feature of modern successful enterprise management.

An important step in improving management is a radical change in the entire planning system. Based on in-depth market research, sales

system, consumer characteristics of goods, and competitiveness, advertising, economic analysis of costs, profits, prices and other indicators, motivational analysis should be planned marketing strategy. This strategy in the form of the formed purposes, the set tasks, a certain sequence of actions finds concrete execution in the marketing program.

Conclusions

The main task of marketing management is to synchronize the process of managing the elements of the marketing complex in such a way that each of them, fulfilling its functional purpose, while improving the efficiency of other elements and thus increase the synergistic effect.

A marketing management system is a set of elements, the relationship of which is ensured by the purposeful action of the subject on the object, which is organized in order to provide the marketing management subsystem of the desired state.

References

1. Senishin OS, Kriveshko OV Marketing: textbook. manual. Lviv: Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, 2020. 347 p.
2. Kotler F. Marketing Management / F. Kotler; lane with English; under ed. O.A. Tretyak, L.A. Volkova, Yu. N. Kapturevsky. Peter, 2000. 896 p.
3. Economic encyclopedic dictionary. URL: <http://subject.com.ua/economic/slovník/4142.html>.
4. Marketing. Textbook / Starostina A.O., Kravchenko V.A., Prygara O.Y., Yarosh-Dmitrenko L.O. / For ed. prof. Starostina A.O. Kyiv: Interservice, 2018. 216 p.
5. Logosha R.V., Polova O.L. Features of formation of marketing strategies of agricultural enterprises. International scientific journal «Internauka». 2018. №11.
6. Lohosha R. V., Gorinska V. M. Improvement of the marketing activity management system of farms. Colloquium—journal. 2021. № 4 (91), czesc 3. P. 40–49.
7. Pisarenko V.V., Bagorka M.O. Strategic marketing: textbook. way. Dnipro: Publisher. 2019. 240 p.
8. Logosha R.V., Semchuk I.A. Identification of marketing models of interaction of agricultural enterprises for biofuel production. Economics of agro-industrial complex. 2020. № 12 (314). P. 45–54.
9. Logosha R.V., Mazur K.V., Krychkovskiy V. Yu. Marketing research of the market of vegetable products in Ukraine: monograph. Vinnytsia: LLC «Tvoru», 2021. 344 p.

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Проблеми формування джерел фінансування при проєктному інвестуванні підприємств та шляхи їх вирішення

Актуальність дослідження. Інвестиційна діяльність виробничого підприємства є стратегічною та тактичною впродовж всього його життєвого циклу і практично зводиться до сукупності циклічно здійснюваних різноманітних проєктів задля забезпечення основної діяльності. Ефективна реалізація будь-якого проєкту залежить зокрема від фінансових ресурсних можливостей. Тому одночасно з вибором стратегічних напрямків інвестиційної діяльності необхідно подбати про формування фінансових джерел для створення інвестиційних ресурсів.

Метою дослідження є окреслення основних проблем формування джерел фінансування при проєктному інвестуванні підприємств та шляхів їх вирішення.

Методи дослідження: систематизації, індукції та дедукції, узагальнення.

Результати дослідження. Сформовані основні підходи до вирішення проблем формування джерел фінансування при проєктному інвестуванні підприємств.

Галузь застосування результатів: результати дослідження можуть застосовуватись у сфері фінансового проєктного забезпечення інвестиційної та загальної діяльності підприємства.

Висновки. В основі раціоналізації інвестиційної діяльності та ефективного прогнозованого формування і витрачання фінансових ресурсів має бути інвестиційна стратегія підприємства, яка ґрунтується на стратегічному виборі на тому чи іншому етапі життєвого циклу. Інвестиційну діяльність підприємства варто розглядати як сукупність різномасштабних інвестиційних проєктів різного призначення, при цьому різноманіття проєктів доцільно привести у відповідність до етапів життєвого циклу підприємства: проєкти започаткування бізнесу, проєкти підтримки функціонування, проєкти зростання, проєкти розвитку. Практично усі проєкти мають позиціонуватись як інноваційні, зокрема це можуть бути стартапи, або інноваційні проєкти з амбіціями стартапу. Сукупність різних проєктів залежно від етапу циклу має свою специфіку фінансування. При цьому мають бути задіяні механізми попереднього та запобіжного формування (зокрема накопичення) джерел фінансування.